

INVOLVEMENT IN SCHOOL CLUBS AND ORGANIZATIONS AND THE COMPETENCE LEVEL OF STUDENT LEADERS

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ABSTRACT

The study was to determine the involvement of the student leaders in school clubs and organizations in terms of virtual/physical involvement, level of awareness of the policies, standards and guidelines of the organization, and organizational involvement. Furthermore, the study attempted to correlate these involvements to students' level of competence in terms of intellectual, interpersonal and physical competence. Using a mixed method design, descriptive-correlational and interview method of research were utilized, it involved the 47 student leaders of Talisay Senior High School, Talisay Batangas during the school year 2020-2021. The data were gathered via online using Google form for the survey and Goggle meet for the focused group discussion. Results revealed that the there was a significant relationship between the involvement in school clubs and organizations and the competence level of student leaders. It can be inferred that the school administration, teachers, and advisers of the organization must give more support to the clubs and organizations by means of financial, giving consideration in time, encouragement, and guidance. On the other hand, the student leaders and students will be aware on how the involvement in school clubs and organizations contribute to their competence level which will be used for their successful learning, living, and working.

Keywords: Involvement, school clubs and organizations, mixed-method, intellectual competence, interpersonal competence, physical competence, Philippines